

USE OF TECHNOLOGY AMONG TEACHERS OF SULU COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY INC.: AN ASSESSMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the use of technology among the teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. It employed descriptive-survey design with 100 teacher-respondents taken through purposive sampling method. The following are findings of this study: The teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. are majority male, married, and in their middle adulthood stage. They have a bachelor's degree as their highest educational attainment; have a high level of agreement with the use of technology in the contexts of Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online; have similar perceptions of the extent of the use of technology in the contexts of Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online, regardless of their gender, age, and civil status. However, there is a significant difference in the perceptions of the teacher-respondents with different educational attainment levels, except for the remote analysis aspect; and have higher perceptions of the extent of automated data collection and online information dissemination than the other groups. The extent of the use of technology in the contexts of Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online are positively and strongly correlated among the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. This study recommends the following: School head of Sulu College of Technology Inc. may provide more support for the teachers to use technology for their professional development and academic performance, such as providing access to online resources, training, and recognition. Teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. may continue to explore and utilize the various benefits of technology for academic activities, such as data collection, analysis, collaboration, and dissemination; and may seek feedback and improvement from their peers and mentors on how to enhance their technology integration skills. Students at Sulu College of Technology Inc may engage actively and constructively with their teachers and classmates to learn and use technology for their academic and personal growth as well

as. Future researchers may conduct further research on the factors that influence the technology use and integration of the teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. on the students, the school, and the society.

Keywords: *Technology; Automated Data Collection; Analysis Collaborate Remotely; Sulu College of Technology; Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Technology is essential in the classroom because it allows for instant access to information. Smart phones, computers, and tablets are already a part of everyday life for both teachers and students. Teachers generally use technology more for preparation and communication than for delivering instruction or assigning learning activities that require the use of technology (Russell et al., 2003). Schwartz (2008) mentioned that teachers learn to exploit technological achievements to teach, transforming the teaching-learning process and enhancing the processes and outcomes of learning. In addition, Murati and Ceka (2017) noted that teachers should use new technology for better quality teaching and make it more interesting, positively improving results for faculty and students.

School management's encouragement is crucial for teachers to continue using technology in teaching, despite challenges like large classrooms and limited resources (Kafyulilo, 2016). Therefore, it is logical to explore the use of these devices in the classroom to enhance learning experiences for students of all ages. By incorporating various types of technology, such as virtual classrooms, students become actively engaged in their learning objectives. Additionally, the use of technology allows for differentiated instruction, catering to the specific needs of each student within the classroom. Aldunate and Nussbaum (2013) concluded that teachers who are early adopters and spend a significant portion of their time incorporating educational technology are more likely to adopt new technology, regardless of its complexity.

The researcher observed that with the utilization of technology in the classroom, students with cellphones are very eager to participate in classroom activities. Good signal provides the students with the needed information in the internet. Somehow, students feel empowered with their learning. The aforementioned articles coupled with observations during class activities encouraged the researcher to conduct research on the utilization of technology in the classroom.

Research Questions

This research study assessed the use of technology among the teachers of Sulu College of Technology Inc. Specifically, this study to answered the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the teacher - respondents of Sulu College of Technology Inc. in terms of:

- 1.1 Age;
- 1.2 Gender;

- 1.3 Civil Status; and
- 1.4 Educational Attainment?
2. What is the extent of the use of technology among teachers of Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of:
 - 2.1 Automated Data Collection;
 - 2.2 Analysis Collaborate Remotely; and
 - 2.3 Disseminate their Findings Online?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers of Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Civil Status; and
 - 3.4 Educational Attainment?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub – categories subsumed under the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of:
 - 4.1 Automated Data Collection;
 - 4.2 Analysis Collaborate Remotely; and
 - 4.3 Disseminate their Findings Online?

METHODS

The researcher had to determine first the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire undergo the validity test first. It was done by the two experts from the academe Once the validity of the survey questionnaire was established, it undergoes the reliability test. It was done with by requesting at least (5) persons who are not respondents of the study. The Cronbach Alpha was computed using the SPSS. If it is 0.70 or above, then the survey questionnaire is reliable. It was then launched to the intended respondents of the study.

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data that was gathered: Frequency and percentage was used for problem 1 since the data gathered are summarized data only Mean and standard deviation was used to answer problem 2 because five-point Likert's scale was used for all statements. T – test for independent sample was used for gender and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to find the significant difference for other variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis, presentation, and interpretation results of this study are based on thorough paper scoring and statistical treatments of the gathered data. These results are aligned with the research questions and the data analysis methods.

Table 1.1. Teacher-respondents' demographic profile based on gender

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	53	53%
Female	47	47%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology based on gender. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, the majority are male, making up 53% (53). Female teacher-respondents account for 47% (47). This means that there is a gender gap of 6% between the male and female groups. This implies a relatively skewed distribution of gender among the teacher-respondents

Table 1.2. Teacher-respondents' demographic profile based on age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
30 years old and below	27	27%
31-40 years old	55	55%
41-50 years old	15	15%
51 years old and above	3	3%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology based on age. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, the majority are between 31-40 years old who make up 55% (55). This is followed by those aged 30 years and below, 41-50 years, and 51 years and above, accounting for 27% (27), 15% (15), and 3% (3) respectively. This shows that the majority of them are in their middle adulthood stage. This means that there is a difference of at least 28% between the other groups. This implies a skewed distribution of age among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.3. Teacher-respondents' demographic profile based on civil status

Civil Status	Number of Respondents	Percent
Single	37	37%
Married	59	59%
Separated/Widowed	4	4%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology based on civil status. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-

respondents, the majority are married who make up 59% (59). This is followed by those who are single, and separated/widowed, accounting for 37% (37), and 4% (4) respectively. This shows that the majority of them are married. This means that there is a difference of at least 22% between the other groups. This implies a skewed distribution of civil status among the teacher-respondents.

Table 1.4. Teacher-respondents' demographic profile based on educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Number of Respondents	Percent
Bachelor's degree	50	50%
With Master's Units	26	26%
Master's Degree	19	19%
With Doctorate Units	5	5%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology based on educational attainment. The table indicates that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 50% have a bachelor's degree. This is followed by those with a master's unit, with master's degree and with doctorate units, accounting for 26% (26), 19% (19), and 5% (5). This shows that the majority of them are bachelor's degree holder. This means that there is a difference of at least 24% between the other groups. This implies a skewed distribution of educational attainment among the teacher-respondents.

Table 2.1. Extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Automated Data Collection

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. The automated data collection tools I use are intuitive and easy to navigate.	3.83	.805	Agree
2. Automated data collection has improved the accuracy of student information records.	3.85	.796	Agree
3. Automated data collection tools have reduced manual errors in data entry.	3.86	.841	Agree
4. Using automated data collection tools has saved me time in managing student data.	3.87	.872	Agree
5. Automated data collection tools have enhanced the security and confidentiality of student records.	3.87	.800	Agree
6. Automated data collection tools provide sufficient flexibility to adapt to different data collection needs.	3.87	.800	Agree
7. I feel confident in using automated data collection tools to gather information for academic purposes.	3.90	.835	Agree

8. Automated data collection tools have improved the comprehensiveness of data collected for assessment purposes.	3.85	.796	Agree
9. The integration of automated data collection tools has streamlined administrative processes within the educational institution.	3.85	.783	Agree
10. Automated data collection tools have facilitated real - time data analysis and decision-making for educational planning.	3.87	.812	Agree
Total	3.862	0.7392	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Partially Agree (PA), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.1 shows the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Automated Data Collection. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.862, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.7392, which indicates that there is some variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents have positive perceptions of using technology in the context of Automated Data Collection.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agree that the automated data collection tools they use are intuitive and easy to navigate, have improved the accuracy of student information records, have reduced manual errors in data entry, have saved them time in managing student data, have enhanced the security and confidentiality of student records, provide sufficient flexibility to adapt to different data collection needs, boost their confidence to gather information for academic purposes, have improved the comprehensiveness of data collected for assessment purposes, have streamlined administrative processes within the educational institution, and have facilitated real - time data analysis and decision-making for educational planning. The result suggests that the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. are satisfied with the use of technology in managing school financial resources and that they recognize its benefits for enhancing transparency and accountability. However, the result also implies that there is room for improvement, as none of the statements have mean scores above 4.00, which would indicate a strong agreement. The teacher-respondents may have some concerns or challenges that prevent them from fully embracing the use of technology in this context.

Table 2.2. Extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Analysis Collaborate Remotely

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. Remote Analysis tools for a comprehensive understanding of the student performance across various subjects or areas.	3.81	.761	Agree
2. Utilizing remote analysis tools has improved my ability to identify learnings gaps among students.	3.82	.770	Agree
3. Remote analysis tools have enabled me to tailor teaching strategies to meet the specific needs of individual students.	3.90	.798	Agree
4. Analyzing student performance remotely has enhanced my ability to track progress over time and identify trends.	3.86	.752	Agree
5. Remote analysis tools have positively influenced my instructional planning and delivery.	3.76	.754	Agree
6. I feel proficient in using remote analysis tools to evaluate student performance and academic trends.	3.78	.773	Agree
7. Remote analysis tools have improved collaboration and data sharing among educators for better decision making.	3.83	.766	Agree
8. Analyzing student performance remotely has positively affected the effectiveness of assessment and examination.	3.82	.757	Agree
9. Remote analysis tools have facilitated early identification of students who may require additional support or intervention.	3.78	.773	Agree
10. Analyzing student performance remotely has contributed to a data driven approach in educational decision - making.	3.81	.787	Agree
Total	3.8170	.69719	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Partially Agree (PA), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.2 shows the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Analysis Collaborate Remotely. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.8170, which indicates an overall rating of “Agree”. The total standard deviation is 0.69719, which indicates that there is some variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teacher-respondents have positive perceptions of using remote analysis tools for various purposes related to teaching and learning.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agree that remote analysis tools help them comprehensively understand the student performance across various subjects or areas, have improved their ability to identify learnings gaps among students, have enabled them to tailor teaching strategies to meet the specific needs of individual students, have enhanced my ability to track progress over time and identify trends, have positively influenced their instructional planning and delivery, make them proficient in using remote analysis tools to evaluate student performance and academic trends, have

improved collaboration and data sharing among educators for better decision making, have positively affected the effectiveness of assessment and examination, have facilitated early identification of students who may require additional support or intervention, and have contributed to a data driven approach in educational decision - making. The result suggests that the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. are satisfied with the use of technology in terms of remote analysis and collaboration. They recognize the benefits of using remote tools for enhancing their effectiveness and efficiency as teachers. However, the result also implies that there is room for improvement, as none of the statements have mean scores above 4.00, which would indicate a strong agreement.

Table 2.3. Extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Disseminate their Findings Online

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1. Online platforms effectively communicate academic updates, events and announcements to students.	3.83	.805	Agree
2. The Online platforms we use provide a user-friendly interface for disseminating academic information.	3.85	.796	Agree
3. Online information dissemination has increased students' engagement and interaction with academic content.	3.89	.827	Agree
4. The use of online platforms for information dissemination has made communication more efficient between educators, students and parents.	3.92	.837	Agree
5. Online platforms effectively convey academic deadlines, assignments and assessment details to students.	3.83	.766	Agree
6. Online information dissemination has made it easier to involve parents in their child's academic progress and school activities.	3.87	.787	Agree
7. The online platforms we utilize ensure the timely dissemination of academic information.	3.85	.770	Agree
8. Online platforms allow for multimedia contents, enhancing the effectiveness for academic information dissemination.	3.82	.757	Agree
9. Online platforms have positively affected students' participation in extracurricular activities and events.	3.86	.792	Agree
10. I feel confident in using online platforms for effective and impact full academic information dissemination.	3.87	.787	Agree
Total	3.8590	.74034	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 3.50-4.49 = Agree (A), 2.50-3.49 = Partially Agree (PA), 1.50-2.49 = Disagree (D), 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

Table 2.3 shows the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the context of Disseminate their Findings Online. The result shows that the total mean score is 3.8590, which indicates an overall rating of "Agree".

The total standard deviation is 0.74034, which indicates that there is some variation among the teacher-respondents in their agreement with the statements. This means that the teachers have positive perceptions of using technology for disseminating academic content and information online.

The mean scores indicate that the teacher-respondents agree that online platforms effectively communicate academic updates, events and announcements to students, provide a user-friendly interface for disseminating academic information, have increased students' engagement and interaction with academic content, have made communication more efficient between educators, students and parents, effectively convey academic deadlines, assignments and assessment details to students, have made it easier to involve parents in their child's academic progress and school activities, ensure the timely dissemination of academic information, allow for multimedia contents, enhancing the effectiveness for academic information dissemination, have positively affected students' participation in extracurricular activities and events, boost their confidence for effective and impact full academic information dissemination. The result suggests that the teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. are satisfied with the use of technology in terms of disseminating their findings online. They recognize the benefits of using online platforms for reaching out to their students, colleagues, and parents. However, the result also implies that there is room for improvement, as none of the statements have mean scores above 4.00, which would indicate a strong agreement.

Table 3.1. Difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description																	
Automated Data Collection	Male	3.8774	.87104	.03268	.225	0.822	Not Significant																	
	Female	3.8447	.56369					Remote Analysis	Male	3.8755	.79540	0.12441	.907	.367	Not Significant	Female	3.7511	.56794	Online Information Dissemination	Male	3.9509	.83358	.19562	1.324
Remote Analysis	Male	3.8755	.79540	0.12441	.907	.367	Not Significant																	
	Female	3.7511	.56794					Online Information Dissemination	Male	3.9509	.83358	.19562	1.324	.189	Not Significant	Female	3.7553	.61106						
Online Information Dissemination	Male	3.9509	.83358	.19562	1.324	.189	Not Significant																	
	Female	3.7553	.61106																					

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.1 presents the difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their gender. The variables include Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online. The table shows that the mean difference and probability values for all

variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the extent of these variables does not affect the perceptions of male and female teacher-respondents differently. This implies that the teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of technology at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the same way regardless of their gender. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of gender." is accepted.

Table 3.2. Difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their age

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Automated Data Collection	Between Groups	3.646	3	1.215	2.313	.081	Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.450	96	.526			
	Total	54.096	99				
Remote Analysis	Between Groups	4.843	3	1.614	3.581*	.017	Significant
	Within Groups	43.279	96	.451			
	Total	48.121	99				
Online Information Dissemination	Between Groups	3.802	3	1.267	2.411	.072	Not Significant
	Within Groups	50.460	96	.526			
	Total	54.262	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their age. The variables include Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for Remote Analysis aspect, are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of teacher-respondents aged 30 years and below on the extent of these variables do not differ from those of teacher-respondents aged 31-40 years, 41-50 years, and 50 years and above, or vice versa. However, on the extent of remote analysis aspect, teacher-respondents aged 31-40 years perceive differently that those aged 50 years and above, vice versa, as show in table 3.2.1. This implies that the teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of technology at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the same way regardless of their age, except for remote analysis aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of age." is accepted.

Table 3.2.1. Multiple comparison of the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. by age

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I - J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Remote Analysis	31-40 years old	30 Years old and below	.03670	.15778	.996
		41-50 years old	.39152	.19558	.195
		51 years old and above	1.08485*	.39808	.038

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in the extent of Remote Analysis when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

On Remote Analysis: It shows that teacher-respondents aged 31-40 years obtained the mean difference of 1.08485* with the Standard Error of .39808 and p-value of .038 over teacher-respondents aged 51 years and above which is significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 3.3. Difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their civil status

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Automated Data Collection	Between Groups	.381	2	.190	.344	.710	Not Significant
	Within Groups	53.715	97	.554			
	Total	54.096	99				
Remote Analysis	Between Groups	.093	2	.047	.094	.910	Not Significant
	Within Groups	48.028	97	.495			
	Total	48.121	99				
Online Information Dissemination	Between Groups	.089	2	.045	.080	.923	Not Significant
	Within Groups	54.173	97	.558			
	Total	54.262	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their civil status. The variables include Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of married teacher-respondents on the extent of these variables do not differ from those of teacher-respondents who are single, and separated/widowed, or vice versa. This implies that the teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of technology at Sulu College of Technology Inc. in the same way regardless of their civil status. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status." is accepted.

Table 3.4. Difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their educational attainment

Sources of Variation		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Automated Data Collection	Between Groups	5.114	3	1.705	3.341*	.022	Significant
	Within Groups	48.981	96	.510			
	Total	54.096	99				
Remote Analysis	Between Groups	3.234	3	1.078	2.306	.082	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.887	96	.468			
	Total	48.121	99				
Online Information Dissemination	Between Groups	4.974	3	1.658	3.229*	.026	Significant
	Within Groups	49.288	96	.513			
	Total	54.262	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.4 presents the difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. based on their educational attainment. The variables include Automated Data Collection, Analysis Collaborate Remotely, and Disseminate their Findings Online. The table shows that the F-values and probability values for all variables, except for remote analysis, are significant at alpha 0.05. This means that the perceptions of teacher-respondents with doctoral units on the extent of automated data collection aspect differ from those of teacher-respondents with bachelor's degree and master's units, or vice versa; and perceptions of teacher-respondents with doctoral units on the extent of online information dissemination differ from those of teacher-respondents with bachelor's degree, master's units, and master's degree, or vice versa.

versa, as shown in table 3.4.1. This implies that the teacher-respondents perceive the extent of the use of technology at Sulu College of Technology Inc. differently depending on their educational attainment, except for remote analysis aspect. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant difference in the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. when data are categorized according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment.” is rejected.

Table 3.4.1. Multiple comparison of the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. by educational attainment

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping Age	Mean Difference (I – J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Automated Data Collection	With Doctoral Units	Bachelor's Degree	.97000*	.33504	.024
		With master's units	1.09231*	.34881	.012
		Master's Degree	.88947	.35902	.070
Online Information Dissemination	With Doctoral Units	Bachelor's Degree	.94200*	.33608	.031
		With aster's units	1.07692*	.34990	.014
		Master's Degree	1.0*	.36015	.033

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to educational attainment have different levels of mean in the extent of Automated Data Collection and Online Information Dissemination when data are grouped according to teacher-respondents' demographic profile in terms of educational attainment.

On Automated Data Collection: It shows that teacher-respondents with doctoral units obtained the mean difference of .97000* with the Standard Error of .33504 and p-value of .024 over teacher-respondents with bachelor's degree; a mean difference of 1.09231* with the Standard Error of .34881 and p-value of .012 over teacher-respondents with master's unit which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

On Online Information Dissemination: It shows that teacher-respondents with doctoral units obtained the mean difference of .94200* with the Standard Error of .33608 and p-value of .031 over teacher-respondents with bachelor's degree; a mean difference of 1.07692* with the Standard Error of .34990 and p-value of .014 over teacher-respondents with master's unit; and a mean difference of 1.0* with the Standard Error of

.36015 and p-value of .033 over teacher-respondents with master's degree which are all significant at alpha 0.05.

Table 4. Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Automated Data Collection	Remote Analysis	.895*	.000	100	Very High
Remote Analysis	Online Information Dissemination	.876*	.000	100	Very High
Automated Data Collection	Online Information Dissemination	.882*	.000	100	Very High

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect

Table 4 presents the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. The table shows that the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson *r*) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05. Based on the table, the following interpretation are as follows:

1. Automated Data Collection and Remote Analysis have a very high positive correlation of .895*. This means that the more the college uses automated data collection methods, the more it can perform remote analysis of the data, and vice versa.
2. Online Information Dissemination and Automated Data Collection have a very high positive correlation of .876*. This means that the more the college uses automated data collection methods, the more it can disseminate information online, and vice versa.
3. Online Information Dissemination and Remote Analysis have a very high positive correlation of .882*. This means that the more the college can perform remote analysis of the data, the more it can disseminate information online, and vice versa.

These correlations are statistically significant, meaning that it is not likely to be due to chance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the use of technology among teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc." is rejected.

Conclusions

1. The demographic profile of the teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology reflects those men are more likely to pursue careers than women and marriage is a common expectation for adults. However, this also suggests that the college may benefit from hiring more diverse and qualified teachers, especially women, and younger teachers, and those with higher degrees, to enhance the quality and diversity of education.
2. The teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. recognize the benefits of using technology for enhancing their professional development and academic performance. They are utilizing technology for various purposes, such as automated Data Collection, analysis collaborate remotely, and disseminate their findings online.
3. The teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. are generally positive and consistent in their views on the use of technology for various academic purposes. However, the level of education may influence their perceptions of some aspects of technology use such as data collection and information dissemination. This suggests that college needs to consider the different needs and preferences of the teacher-respondents with different educational backgrounds to enhance their technology integration skills.
4. The teacher-respondents at Sulu College of Technology Inc. have a high level of technology integration in their academic activities. They use technology for various purposes, such as data collection, collaborate analysis remotely, and information dissemination.

Recommendations

This study recommended the following:

1.School head of Sulu College of Technology Inc. may provide more support for the teachers to use technology for their professional development and academic performance, such as providing access to online resources, training, and recognition.

2.Teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. may continue to explore and utilize the various benefits of technology for academic activities, such as data collection, analysis, collaboration, and dissemination.

3.Teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. may seek feedback and improvement from their peers and mentors on how to enhance their technology integration skills.

4.Students at Sulu College of Technology Inc may engage actively and constructively with their teachers and classmates to learn and use technology for their academic and personal growth as well as.

5.Future researchers may conduct further research on the factors that influence the technology use and integration of the teachers at Sulu College of Technology Inc. on the students, the school, and the society.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher followed the ethical guidelines throughout the research process. The data collected from the respondents were treated with utmost confidentiality.

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REFERENCES

- Aldunate, R., & Nussbaum, M. (2013). Teacher adoption of technology. *Comput. Hum. Behav.*, 29, 519-524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2012.10.017>.
- Kafyulilo, A., Fisser, P., & Voogt, J. (2016). Factors affecting teachers' continuation of technology use in teaching. *Education and Information Technologies*, 21, 1535-1554. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-015-9398-0>.
- Murati, R., & Ceka, A. (2017). The Use of Technology in Educational Teaching. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8, 197-199.

- Russell, M., Bebell, D., O'Dwyer, L., & O'connor, K. (2003). Examining Teacher Technology Use. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 54, 297 - 310.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487103255985>.
- Schwartz, N. (2008). Exploiting the Use of Technology to Teach. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 40, 389 - 404.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2008.10782513>.